

HYDROXYAPATITE–POLYETHYLENE COMPOSITES FOR BONE SUBSTITUTION: EFFECTS OF HYDROSTATIC EXTRUSION

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SUMMARY: Hydroxyapatite reinforced high density polyethylene composites (HAPEX™) were hydrostatically extruded at different extrusion ratios. Their structure and mechanical properties were subsequently evaluated using various techniques. It was found that the uniform distribution of particulate hydroxyapatite in polyethylene achieved by compounding was not altered by hydrostatic extrusion. Substantial increases in the tensile properties of both filled and unfilled polyethylene were obtained in the extrusion direction. For HAPEX™ with a fixed volume fraction of hydroxyapatite, it was evident that the higher the extrusion ratio, the stronger and the stiffer the composite rod. Hydrostatically extruded HAPEX™ possesses mechanical properties that are within the bounds for human cortical bone, which indicates the potential for its load-bearing skeletal implant applications.

KEYWORDS: hydroxyapatite, polyethylene, biomaterial, hydrostatic extrusion, structure, properties

INTRODUCTION

Hydroxyapatite (HA) reinforced high density polyethylene (HDPE) composites (HAPEX™) have been developed as a bone analogue for medical applications [1]. HAPEX™ containing 40% by volume of HA possesses a stiffness approaching the lower bound of human cortical bone together with a superior fracture toughness [2]. This has led to its clinical applications such as orbital floor reconstruction [3]. The *in vivo* study showed that HAPEX™ encourages bone apposition rather than fibrous tissue encapsulation on a skeletal implant [4]. A particular advantage of HAPEX™ is that the implant can be easily shaped interoperatively for individual patients, while modification of implants made of bioactive ceramics or glasses is difficult in an operating theatre. Major progress is currently made in USA using HAPEX™ implants for otologic and maxillo-facial surgery.

For major load bearing applications, it is necessary to increase substantially the stiffness and strength of HAPEX™. Chemical coupling of HA to HDPE has resulted in improved mechanical behaviour but only limited increases in tensile properties [5]. More significant levels of improvement, however, are required.

It has long been recognised that molecular orientation in a polymer leads to a significant enhancement in the stiffness and strength along the orientation direction, as well as producing material anisotropy [6]. These effects are particularly evident with polyethylene due to its simple molecular structure [7,8]. The increase in tensile modulus has been correlated with the

average longitudinal crystal thickness in the ultra-oriented polyethylene [9]. Among several well established technologies for inducing molecular orientation in polymeric materials, hydrostatic extrusion has been used to increase substantially the tensile strength and modulus of polyethylene [8], which results in orienting the polyethylene molecules and transforming the spherulites into the fibre structure in the extruded material. It is therefore natural to investigate the possibility of hydrostatic extrusion of HAPEX™ and its effects on HAPEX™.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Materials and Composite Processing

Synthetic HA (Grade P88, Plasma Biotol Ltd, UK) and an HDPE (Rigidex HM4560XP, BP Chemicals Ltd, UK) were used to produce HAPEX™ with 40% by volume of HA. Compression moulded HAPEX™ billets were manufactured via the established route [10]. Unfilled HDPE was also processed through the same procedure as a control.

The technology of hydrostatic extrusion of polyethylene (and hence HAPEX™ in the current investigation) has been described elsewhere [11]. Briefly, it involves surrounding a billet of the material with a fluid, heating up the billet to below its melting temperature and extruding the billet through a convergent die at a constant speed by pressurising the fluid. The extrusion ratio (ER) is defined as the ratio of the cross-sectional area of the billet to that of the die bore. Extrusion ratios of 5:1 and 8:1 were achieved by altering the billet and die diameters.

Methods

The hydrostatically extruded rods were cut to 50mm in length, machined into specimens to conform to ASTM E466, embedded at two ends in an epoxy resin to facilitate gripping and subjected to tensile testing on an Instron 6025 machine (Figure 1). Specimen extension was measured with an extensometer and this value was used to calculate the Young's modulus. The specimens were tested to failure and the tensile strength and fracture strain were determined.

Compression moulded materials were also tensile tested according to ISO 527, using dumbbell specimens made from square plaques. The values obtained were used as properties of HDPE and HAPEX™ at the nominal extrusion ratio of 1:1.

The distribution of HA particles in the HDPE matrix was investigated for HAPEX™ after compression moulding and hydrostatic extrusion. The polished surfaces, prepared by a standardised method [10], were lightly gold coated and examined under a JEOL 6300 scanning electron microscope (SEM). Tensile fracture surfaces of hydrostatically extruded HAPEX™ were also examined.

The molecular mass of the HDPE matrix at each processing stage was analysed by high temperature gel permeation chromatography (GPC). The measurements were made using a Waters 150CV instrument, operating at 140• C and with 1,2-dichlorobenzene as the solvent (allowance being made for the presence of filler).

Figure 1 Hydrostatically extruded samples after machining, embedding and tensile testing

RESULTS

A homogeneous distribution of HA particles in HDPE matrix was found in both the centre and edge of hydrostatically extruded HAPEX™ rods at all extrusion ratios. Comparing the SEM micrographs taken from polished surfaces (perpendicular as well as parallel to the extrusion direction) with results obtained previously [10], it appears that hydrostatic extrusion did not alter the dispersion and distribution characteristics of HA in HAPEX™ which had been achieved by compounding using the twin screw extruder.

Figure 2: Tensile stress-strain curve of HAPEX™ hydrostatically extruded at the extrusion ratio of 5:1

Figure 2 shows the stress-strain curve of HAPEX™ hydrostatically extruded at ER = 5:1. HDPE and HAPEX™ samples extruded at ER = 8:1 also exhibited the same mechanical behaviour. Under an increasing tensile load, the extruded rod deformed with a gradually decreasing tangent modulus up to a certain stress level above which a near-constant tangent modulus was maintained. The rod usually fractured in this near-constant modulus region, the

fracture point depending on the volume fraction of HA and the extrusion ratio. Tensile testing results for unfilled HDPE and HAPEX™ before and after hydrostatic extrusion are listed in Table 1. Higher extrusion ratios led to higher Young's modulus and tensile strength for both HDPE and HAPEX™. The fracture strain of HAPEX™ was also substantially increased by hydrostatic extrusion, rising from 2.6% at ER = 1:1 (Sample CM40.1) to 9.4% at ER = 8:1 (Sample PC40.7). It was observed that higher modulus and strength values could be obtained from unmachined (i.e. without removal of skin of the rod) specimens than from machined (i.e. with skin being removed) specimens.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of hydrostatically extruded HDPE and HAPEX™ before and after hydrostatic extrusion

Sample Code	HA Volume (%)	Extrusion Ratio	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)
CM0.1	0	1:1	0.65	17.89
PC0.100	0	5:1	2.59	61.24
PC0.24	0	8:1	4.08	158.2
CM40.1	40	1:1	4.29	20.67
PC40.1	40	5:1	5.89	64.78
PC40.7	40	8:1	9.91	91.23
PI40.2 *	40	8:1	11.4	80.84

* hydrostatically extruded sample using a billet made by injection moulding

Table 2 Weight average molecular mass of HDPE in HAPEX™ after hydrostatic extrusion

HA Volume (%)	Weight Average Molecular Mass of HDPE		
	ER = 1:1	ER = 5:1	ER = 8:1
0	271000	244000	248000
40	212000	174000	176000

* $M_w = 270000$ for as-received HDPE

The weight average molecular mass (M_w) of hydrostatically extruded HDPE and HAPEX™ is listed in Table 2. It seems that hydrostatic extrusion caused reductions in M_w . However, the extrusion ratio (5:1 or 8:1) did not appear to affect significantly the molecular mass of HDPE. (All the HDPE and HAPEX™ samples were extruded at 115°C, but with different extrusion pressures which are dependent on the extrusion ratio.)

SEM examination of fracture surfaces revealed that a core-skin structure, as shown in Figure 3a, existed in hydrostatically extruded HAPEX™. The skin may not be concentric with the centre of the rod as a varying thickness of the skin was found around the core. Figure 3b shows the skin area of the fracture surface of HAPEX™ extruded at ER = 8:1.

Figure 3 Tensile fracture surface of HAPEX™ hydrostatically extruded at the extrusion ratio of 8:1 , (a) a general view, (b) the skin region

DISCUSSION

Hydrostatic extrusion orients the molecular chain of polyethylene and transforms the previously folded chain morphology into one comprising extended molecular chains. Due to the high filler content (i.e. 40% by volume of HA, which is 69% by weight), HAPEX™ was hydrostatically extruded at extrusion pressures two to three times higher than for the unfilled HDPE. The extrusion temperature rather than the extrusion pressure seems to affect the

molecular weight of the HDPE matrix of HAPEX™ with a fixed HA volume fraction. It appears that hydrostatic extrusion not only improves the tensile properties of both filled and unfilled polymer in the extrusion direction but also changes their mechanical behaviour. For all the extruded rods, there are two distinctive regions as far as their tensile curves are concerned (Figure 2). Such tensile characteristics differ greatly from the behaviour of both filled and unfilled polyethylene prepared without hydrostatic extrusion. Compression moulded HDPE undergoes yielding and necking under tension, while compression moulded HAPEX™ with 40% of HA exhibits a near-linear tensile curve before fracture [10].

At the microstructural level, the investigation into the distribution of HA particles in hydrostatically extruded HAPEX™ rods has revealed the same (or at least highly similar) dispersion and distribution characteristics of hydroxyapatite in the polymer matrix as that in compression moulded samples, both exhibiting good dispersion and uniform distribution of HA particles. However, at the macrostructural level, although hydrostatic extrusion probably does not result in a core-skin structure for the unfilled polymer, it gives rise to such a structure in filled polyethylene, which has been verified by both tensile testing and SEM examination. The skin is stiffer than the core, which accounts for higher modulus values of unmachined specimen than those of machined specimen from the same sample. The thickness of the skin is probably influenced by both the ceramic particle volume fraction and the extrusion ratio.

It is evident for HDPE or HAPEX™ with a fixed HA volume fraction that the higher the extrusion ratio, the stronger and the stiffer the extruded rod (Figure 4). With an extrusion ratio of 8:1, the Young's modulus and tensile strength of HAPEX™ are 2.6 and 4.4 times higher than those of compression moulded material. An additional benefit of hydrostatic extrusion is the substantial increase in fracture strain (a measure of ductility) which is far greater than that of human cortical bone (9.4% vs 0.5-3.0%). It is also necessary to bear in mind that materials need to be processed through the compounding extruder in order to achieve larger property improvements.

Hydrostatically extruded HAPEX™ possesses mechanical properties which are within the bounds for human cortical bone. This is remarkable because the possibility of load bearing applications of HAPEX™ can now be explored. Currently, it is ideal that implants are made without removing the skin of hydrostatically extruded composites to avoid any uncertainty regarding their structure and mechanical properties. Further research in die design and optimisation of processing conditions may lead to hydrostatic extrusion of a structurally and mechanically homogeneous HAPEX™, as experience has shown that there is an optimum combination of extrusion temperature and pressure that results in the highest stiffness of polyethylene [12].

Figure 4 Effect of hydrostatic extrusion on Young's modulus and tensile strength of HDPE and HAPEXTM with 40% of HA

CONCLUSIONS

Hydroxyapatite reinforced high density polyethylene composite (HAPEXTM) containing 40% by volume of hydroxyapatite particles has been successfully hydrostatically extruded at different extrusion ratios. The resultant composite possesses mechanical properties that are within the bounds for human cortical bone together with a significantly improved ductility (and hence toughness). Therefore, HAPEXTM further processed via hydrostatic extrusion shows great promise for major load bearing skeletal implant applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Mr.V.Ford, Mrs.J.Huang and Dr.S.Holding (RAPRA) for their technical assistance. Dr.N.H.Ladizesky is thanked for hydrostatically extruding HDPE and HAPEXTM. Support from the UK EPSRC is gratefully acknowledged.

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